

1 Multiscale Modeling for Coastal Cities: Addressing Climate Change 2 Impacts on Flood Events at Urban-Scale

3
4 Michele Bendoni¹, Francesca Caparrini², Andrea Cucco³, Stefano Taddei⁴, Iulia Anton⁵, Roberta Paranunzio⁶, Rossella Mocali⁴,
5 Massimo Perna⁴, Michele Sacco⁴, Giovanni Vitale^{8,4}, Manuela Corongiu⁴, Alberto Ortolani^{7,4}, Salem Gharbia⁵, Carlo Brandini^{8,4}.

6
7 1. Institute of Marine Science, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ISMAR), Forte Santa Teresa, snc, 19032 - Lerici (SP),
8 Italy.

9 2. Institute of Geosciences and Earth Resources, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-IGG), Via G. Moruzzi 1, 56124 - Pisa
10 (PI), Italy.

11 3. Institute for the study of Anthropic Impacts and Sustainability in marine environment, National Research Council (CNR- IAS),
12 Loc. Sa Mardini Torregrande - Oristano, Italy.

13 4. LaMMA Consortium, Via Madonna del Piano 10, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino (FI), Italy.

14 5. Atlantic Technological University, Ash Lane F91 YW50, Sligo, Ireland.

15 6. Institute of Atmospheric Sciences and Climate, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ISAC), Corso Fiume, 4, 10133 Torino
16 (TO), Italy.

17 7. Institute of Bio-Economy, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-IBE), Via Madonna del Piano 10, 50019 Sesto Fiorentino
18 (FI), Italy.

19 8. Institute of Marine Science, National Research Council of Italy (CNR-ISMAR), Via Madonna del Piano 10, 50019 Sesto
20 Fiorentino (FI), Italy.

21 Corresponding Author: Carlo Brandini, brandini@lamma.toscana.it, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6509-4533>

22 Abstract

23
24 This study presents an integrated modeling framework designed to bridge scales from regional to urban,
25 enabling a detailed assessment of the impacts of future climate scenarios on three European coastal cities:
26 Massa (Italy) and Vilanova (Spain) in the Mediterranean, and Oarsoaldea (Spain) in the Atlantic. Conducted
27 as part of the SCORE EU Project (*Smart Control of Climate Resilience in European Coastal Cities*), the
28 framework employs a novel, non-standard downscaling approach to translate large-scale atmospheric
29 outputs from the EURO-CORDEX regional model ALADIN63 (for Historical, RCP4.5, and RCP8.5
30 scenarios) into high-resolution simulations of storm surges, wave climate, and river discharge using
31 SHYFEM, WAVEWATCH III, and LISFLOOD models.

32 The framework achieves coastal resolutions on the order of 100 m, providing time series of water levels
33 and wave runup, which are combined into total water levels. These results, together with extreme value
34 analysis of river discharge and projected relative sea level rise (RSLR), are used as boundary conditions for
35 an urban-scale hydrodynamic model with resolutions as fine as 2–20 m. This multi-scale integration allows
36 for detailed analysis of changes in flooded areas and volumes under RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, relative
37 to historical conditions, highlighting the influence of shifting extremes, RSLR, and site-specific features.

38 Results show that in Massa and Vilanova, increased extreme river discharges are projected, while moderate
39 changes in extreme water levels are overshadowed by RSLR, particularly for Massa. Oarsoaldea, well
40 protected from storm surges, is expected to experience a slight reduction in extreme river discharge. This
41 work demonstrates the capability of the integrated framework to address climate change impacts at urban
42 scales, providing valuable insights for the development of localized adaptation strategies.

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44 **1 Introduction**

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46 Rapid urban growth and climate change are two of the most pressing challenges of our time (Satterthwaite,
47 2009), especially in coastal regions, where their combination significantly increases the exposure of urban
48 areas to extreme natural events. Coastal cities and settlements, home to more than 2 billion people
49 worldwide, are among the most vulnerable areas to these events (IPCC, 2023; Vitousek et al., 2017;
50 Oppenheimer et al., 2019). Approximately 900 million people live in low-elevation coastal zones (LECZ),
51 areas situated less than 10 m above mean sea level (Reimann et al., 2023), with a projected global population
52 density of around 400-500 people/square km by 2060 (Neumann et al., 2015). These regions, marked by
53 increasing anthropogenic activity, hold crucial social and economic importance, with dense population and
54 infrastructure that may further elevate their future vulnerability (Figueiredo et al., 2024; Paranunzio et al.,
55 2022). Global mean sea level is projected to rise between 0.3 and 2 m by 2100 under scenarios of increasing
56 global warming (Vitousek et al., 2017). In addition, the effects of land subsidence are expected to further
57 exacerbate risks in most coastal areas, intensifying future impacts on population and infrastructure
58 (Vousdoukas et al., 2018).

59 In Europe alone, currently, over 50 million live in LECZ areas (Vousdoukas et al., 2020). With a relative
60 sea level rise (RSLR) of just 0.15 m above 2020 levels, the coastal population potentially exposed to a 100-
61 year coastal flood could increase by about 20% in the medium to long term (IPCC, 2023). By 2100, the
62 total number of people exposed to risk of flooding is projected to reach 1.61 million, and 3.9 million, under
63 the two Representative Concentration Pathways (RCP) scenarios 4.5 and 8.5 (Vousdoukas et al., 2020).

64 Coastal cities around the world are threatened not only from inundation due to storm surges or sea level
65 rise (Hallegatte et al., 2013; Wahl et al., 2017) but also from river flooding which poses additional risk
66 (Khanal et al., 2019). These areas are therefore impacted by a complex interplay of multiple flood-related
67 systems including river, sea/oceans and coastal land (Laino et al., 2024). Assessing the local effects of such
68 hazards to enhance coastal communities' resilience is one of the greatest challenges of our time, especially
69 in the context of the ongoing climate change. High uncertainty in urban sprawl and flood risks leads to a
70 generalized lack of preparedness to face future flood events (Sun et al., 2022). In this context, high-
71 resolution climate data are essential for defining downscaling strategies that begin with global climate
72 services and are able to evaluate the impacts of multiple hazards at the local scale. Bensi et al. (2020)
73 provides a broad overview of existing literature on hazard interaction, organized by different flooding
74 hazard focus, i.e., studies that address several mechanisms in the fluvial and coastal flood processes alone
75 and studies focusing on joint fluvial and coastal flood processes (e.g., Masina et al., 2015; Bevacqua et al.,
76 2017). Many studies address the degree of dependence among different mechanisms, e.g., precipitation,
77 river flow and storm surge events to assess coastal flood risk, also investigating how it changes over time
78 (Bevacqua et al., 2017; Mofstakhari et al. 2017; Orton et al., 2018; Zheng et al., 2013) and with respect to
79 different climate change scenarios (e.g., Parodi et al. 2020; Zhong et al., 2023; Gori & Lin, 2022; Wahl et
80 al., 2015).

81 Despite the large number of methodologies, tools and models exploring the single or combined effect of
82 climate-related hazards in coastal areas worldwide, studies which exploit different approaches to provide a
83 global multidisciplinary framework to assess flood scenarios in the future at the fine resolution of the urban
84 scale are not widespread (Bensi et al., 2020). Some promising studies pointing in this direction have been
85 developed during the last decade, especially in the US. Based on copulas and bivariate dependence analysis,
86 Mofstakhari et al. (2017) quantified the increases in failure probabilities of coastal flood defenses for eight
87 estuarine systems along the coasts of United States caused by RSLR under multiple flood drivers ad RCP4.5

88 and RCP8.5 in 2030 and 2050. To assess climate impacts for the US West Coast, Barnard et al. (2014) used
89 wind fields from different Global Circulation Models (GCMs) under two RCPs scenarios, 4.5 and 8.5, to
90 resolve 3 hours peak conditions into the WAVEWATCH III wave models within a deterministic,
91 multidimensional framework in the Coastal Storm Modeling System (CoSMoS). Process-based modeling
92 system proved to be able to dynamically transfer information from global atmospheric scale to the regional
93 and local scale to predict impacts of multiple coastal hazards (i.e., coastal erosion and cliff failures and
94 flooding) for a range of RSLR and storm scenarios at a resolution scale that is relevant for management and
95 adaptation planning (meters scale) (Barnard et al., 2019). In Europe, some few attempts have been made to
96 develop comprehensive models that scale down from the synoptic to the urban scale. Model framework to
97 assess the coastal risks and morphological impacts induced by extreme storm events similar to CoSMoS
98 has been developed in the context of European projects (e.g., Ciavola et al., 2011), but more in support of
99 early warning and emergency response. Van den Hurk et al. (2015) studied the joint distribution of
100 precipitation and storm surges for 1950 to 2000 using 800 years of simulated data using a RACMO2
101 Regional Circulation Model (RCM) at 12 km resolution to establish a relation between compound hazards
102 in the Netherlands.

103 It follows that high resolution RCMs are needed to properly model climate impact at a higher resolution.
104 Estimating the impacts of climate change on coastal cities requires increasing the resolution of city-scale
105 models to unprecedented levels, simulating coastal and terrestrial flood conditions for different return
106 periods and scenarios, and including considerations for the evaluation of financial resilience strategies or
107 ecosystem-based adaptation solutions. Thus, a multidisciplinary framework is needed to foster, through co-
108 participatory and co-creative approach, the public engagement of scientists, policy-makers and citizens, to
109 identify and share socially and technically acceptable solutions. This is part of SCORE project (Smart
110 control of climate resilience in European coastal cities, <https://score-eu-project.eu/>) which aims, through an
111 integrated and multidisciplinary approach, to monitor and validate reliable and robust adaptation measures
112 in low-lying coastal cities to minimize the effects of climate-related hazards and enhance the overall
113 resilience. This is addressed in the context of the Coastal City Living Labs (CCLLs), a novel participatory
114 approach built upon the living lab concept that aims to involve scientists, decision makers, citizens and
115 different stakeholders in the modeling process and in preparing climate risk assessment analysis, thus
116 accelerating the systematic adoption (Paranunzio et al., 2023).

117 To assess the impacts of multiple climate-related hazards on coastal cities under different climate change
118 scenarios, we present a downscaling procedure which consists of a dynamic multi-branch modeling chain
119 ending with high-resolution (~2 m) flood simulations. Here, we use the term “downscaling” to indicate the
120 transfer of information from the synoptic atmospheric scale to the urban scale of individual buildings and
121 streets, rather than the increase in detail of a specific dataset coming from a numerical model with higher
122 spatial and temporal resolution with respect to the parent one. An integrated approach blending
123 oceanography, hydrology, hydraulics and extreme value analysis (EVA) has been used for the computation
124 of flooded areas for both historical periods and future climate projections for different return periods and
125 under two different RCP scenarios, 4.5 and 8.5 (IPCC, 2014). We used atmospheric data from an EURO-
126 CORDEX RCM (Jacob et al., 2014), and three different models simulating the evolution of water level,
127 wave dynamics, and rainfall-runoff transformation to create the boundary conditions to run hydrodynamic
128 simulations in coastal cities, for both past and future periods. The modeling chain has been applied to the
129 three different CCLLs based on the indications of the SCORE Project: Massa (Italy), Vilanova i la Geltrú
130 and Oarsoaldea (Spain), as different test cases characterized by different phenomenological features.

131 The high computational demand of the simulation and the need for an extremely fine temporal resolution
132 data are two major challenges in this context. Among the EURO-CORDEX models, only one RCM offers
133 at least three-hourly data for the atmospheric variables required across all models and scenarios. We
134 acknowledge that the use of a multi-RCM (GCM) ensemble is preferable with respect to a single RCM
135 (GCM) to predict more rigorously spatial patterns and to estimate the uncertainty in the projections in
136 response to climate change (Khanal et al., 2019; Gori & Lin, 2022; Bevacqua et al, 2020; Ghanbari et al,
137 2021). However, the computational cost of the procedure and the high-resolution of the model create
138 challenges for multi-model impact assessment at urban scale. In addition, some studies make successful use
139 of one GCM in dynamical downscaling and hydrological modeling (Vezzoli et al., 2015; Lima et al., 2023).
140 To our knowledge, this is one of the first works for the European area dealing with projections of climate
141 data at i) such a high spatio-temporal resolution, ii) exploiting various computational demanding models
142 up to the urban scale, iii) seeking to develop a flood hazard modeling chain from multiple sources and iv)
143 embracing a multidisciplinary modeling framework.

144 The work is organized as follows. Section 2 provides a brief overview of the project and description of the
145 study sites. Section 3 describes the overall methodology, while Section 4 deals specifically with the
146 implementation of the three numerical models. Section 5 describes the extreme value analysis and the urban
147 scale model. Results of the overall methodology are then presented in Section 6 and discussed in the next
148 section. Section 8 is dedicated to conclusion on outlook.

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150

151 **2 The SCORE Project and the study sites**

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153 The SCORE project focuses on the resilience of coastal cities to the effects of climate change. Coastal
154 cities, as climate change hotspots, are affected by numerous consequences resulting from changes in the
155 marine, atmospheric, and terrestrial (hydrogeological) components of the Earth system. However, among
156 the many risks related to climate change in coastal cities (which could include increasing marine and
157 atmospheric heatwaves, fire risks, subsidence due to the over-exploitation of water resources in tourist
158 areas, etc.), SCORE has focused on flood risk. This includes flooding from rivers, marine inundations, or a
159 combination of both. Marine floods, as is well known, can result not only from extreme storm surges but
160 from combinations of storm waves and high tidal levels (both astronomical and meteorological induced by
161 wind and pressure), following a signal that is modulated in the long term by RSLR.

162 The selection of cities involved in the project was made during the project development phase. The choice
163 was not driven by prioritizing cities with the highest exposure to these effects (e.g., the city of Venice), but
164 rather those where there is an active and engaged community of citizens, stakeholders, and research centers
165 collaborating on co-designing solutions to improve resilience to the effects of climate change. This process
166 begins with ecosystem-based adaptation solutions (EbAs; Munang et al., 2013; Temmerman et al., 2013;
167 Tiwari et al., 2022), which encourage practices that increase citizen participation and awareness, such as
168 sharing meteorological observations following Citizen Science standards (Conrad & Hilchey, 2010). The
169 modeling components developed for these cities also contribute to the creation of urban-scale Digital Twins,
170 which are part of a specific activity within the project. These digital tools, alongside advanced data
171 representation, enable a better understanding of flood effects and allow the modeling of adaptation scenarios
172 using a What-If methodology (Paranunzio et al., 2023).

173 Within the project, local initiatives are built following the Living Lab paradigm (Bulkeley et al., 2018),
174 forming Coastal Cities Living Labs, where local communities participate according to the quadruple helix

175 model (Carayannis & Campbell, 2009). The decision of whether cities would act as frontrunners or
176 followers for certain project activities (as organized through the project work packages) was made based
177 on the specific themes of interest within the CCLLs.

178 Therefore, the selection of the study cases presented in this article: Massa, Vilanova i la Geltrú (from now
179 on we will refer to the city simply as Vilanova), Oarsoaldea (Figure 1) was based on the presence of three
180 frontrunners that followed a common analysis methodology, which is described in the next section. This
181 methodology starts from the availability of data provided by climate services and, through downscaling
182 techniques and urban and coastal hydraulic modeling, defines the design conditions expected for coastal
183 cities. Defining case studies based on project guidance does not diminish the scientific value of this work
184 or the approach used; rather, it demonstrates how the problem of coastal resilience is universal and not
185 restricted to specific areas. Ultimately, this requires a careful analysis that can be more effectively carried
186 out with a local and site-specific approach rather than relying solely on regional models, even when they
187 have high-resolution.

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190 **Fig 1** View of the geographical area where the analyzed cities are located. Base map: Google Satellite imagery (©
191 Google 2024; Imagery © CNES / Airbus, Maxar Technologies, Airbus)

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193 **3 Overall methodology**

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195 The modeling chain implemented transfers information from the atmospheric synoptic scale (1000-100 km)
196 up to the urban scale (2 m), and is aimed at obtaining time series of wave height H_s , water level η , and river
197 discharge Q close to the coastal cities of interest, for both past periods and future climate projections. An
198 extreme value analysis is then performed on the calculated time series to estimate the peak values associated
199 with specific return periods. These values are eventually employed to build synthetic events to simulate
200 their effects in terms of flooded areas for the analyzed coastal cities. A sketch of the overall procedure is
201 reported in Figure 2.

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Fig 2 Sketch reporting the overall methodology to downscale data and run hydrodynamic simulations at the urban scale. Light red boxes correspond to the models employed to downscale atmospheric variables, light green boxes contain variables subject to extreme value analysis and the light blue box corresponds to the urban scale flood modeling part. H_s is the significant wave height, T_p is the peak wave period, Q is the river discharge, η is the water level, $\Delta\eta_{Tide}$ and $\Delta\eta_{RSLR}$ are the increases in water level due to tide and relative sea level rise, respectively

The modeling chain implemented employs atmospheric data from the ALADIN63 RCM (Coppola et al., 2020; Vautard et al., 2020), provided by the EURO-CORDEX experiment (Jacob et al., 2014), and use it as input for the following models: WaveWatch III (WW3DG, 2019) simulates the dynamic of wave height taking as input the surface zonal and meridional wind velocities (uas , vas); SHYFEM (Umgiesser et al., 2004) simulates the evolution of water levels forced by surface winds (uas , vas) and mean sea level pressure (psl); LISFLOOD (Van Der Knijff et al., 2008) simulates the rainfall-runoff transformation and takes in input several atmospheric variables such as rainfall rate (pr), air temperature ($tair$), specific humidity ($huss$), sea level pressure (psl) shortwave and longwave radiation ($rsds$, $rlds$, $rsus$, $rlus$). A more detailed and thorough description of the downscaling procedure for each variable is reported in Sections 4.1, 4.2 and 4.3.

For each of the models, the Evaluation, Historical, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 experiments are simulated. The Evaluation (Eval) experiment is employed to test the ability of the model to reproduce observable extreme events. In such a case the ALADIN63 RCM is forced by the ERA-Interim reanalysis (Dee et al., 2011). The Historical (Hist) experiment is used as a baseline for the two climate change scenarios expressed by the Representative Concentration Pathways defined by the fifth Assessment Report (AR5) of

225 Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC, 2014). RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 data are used to analyze
 226 the effect of anthropogenic climate change in the future flooding pattern at urban scale. For this set of
 227 simulations, the ALADIN63 RCM was forced by the CNRM-CM5 GCM (Voldoire et al., 2011). The choice
 228 of such a RCM is due to the fact that this was the only one that provided at least three-hourly data for the
 229 atmospheric forcing variables for all the experiments, among the EURO-CORDEX models. Other RCMs
 230 provided those variables at different output frequencies or solely for specific temporal windows (e.g.
 231 RCP4.5 for the period 2050-2070 and RCP8.5 for the period 2030-2050). The consequences and limitations
 232 of such a choice are discussed in Section 7.

233 A summary of the simulated experiments with associated time windows is reported in Table 1.
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Experiment	Time window	Simulated RP [years]
Eval	1980-2012	-
Hist	1956-2005	25, 100
RCP4.5	2006-2100	25, 100 (2011-2060) 25, 100 (2051-2100)
RCP8.5	2006-2100	25, 100 (2011-2060) 25, 100 (2051-2100)

235 Table 1. Summary of the simulated experiments with associated time windows. Return periods (RP) refer to the values calculated
 236 through the extreme value analysis and used to create synthetic events simulated with the urban scale hydrodynamic model.
 237

238 The hydrodynamic simulations of storm surges and river flood at urban scale have been performed using
 239 the HEC-RAS 6.4 model (Brunner & US Army Corps of Engineers, 2021), similarly to Gori and Lin (2022).
 240 The storm surge is modeled following a simplified approach consisting of the combination of time series
 241 of wave runup $R_{2\%}$ and water level. First, the wave runup $R_{2\%}$ is determined using wave height and period
 242 and the slope of the beach, following Atkinson et al. (2017), then, it is added to the water level η , to obtain
 243 the total water level η_{TOT} . The extreme value analysis is carried out on this last variable and on the river
 244 discharge Q , separately, for all the simulated experiments (Table 1). Hazard maps reporting the water depth
 245 envelope associated with a specific return period event are produced for the flood due to the storm surge
 246 and for the riverine flood. Furthermore, to simulate the RSLR and the effect of the tide, an increased value
 247 for the mean water level is applied to each hydrodynamic simulation based on the associated experiment.
 248 A more detailed description of the urban scale hydrodynamic modeling activity is reported in Section 5.

249 The projections of RSLR for RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 used in this paper can be found in two free-access datasets
 250 (Vousdoukas et al. 2016a for RCP4.5 data, Vousdoukas et al. 2016b for RCP8.5 data), downloadable from
 251 the European Commission Joint Research Centre (JRC) website. These datasets provide the Total Water
 252 Level (TWL), from which the RSLR can be extracted by subtracting the episodic extremes (wave runup
 253 and storm surge level) which are also provided, along with the tidal contribution. More information can be
 254 found in the related article (Vousdoukas et al. 2017). The dataset covers the European coastlines with a
 255 temporal resolution of 10 years. Europe is divided into 10 regions, within which all values are averaged.
 256 All values are given with respect to the 1985–2005 reference period.

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259 **4 Modeling branches**

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261 In this section, we describe the implementation of the three numerical models: WaveWatch III, SHYFEM
262 and LISFLOOD, employed to perform the main part of the downscaling procedure. Each of the models has
263 a particular setup on the basis of the analyzed coastal city.

264

265 **4.1 Wave climate model**

266 The numerical model used to simulate wind waves was WaveWatch III (WAVE-height, WATer depth and
267 Current Hindcasting), v. 6.07 (WW3DG, 2019), a community third-generation wave model developed at
268 the US National Centers for Environmental Prediction (NOAA/NCEP) that includes the latest scientific
269 advancements in the field of wind-wave modeling and dynamics (<https://github.com/NOAA-EMC/WW3/releases/download/6.07/wwatch3.v6.07.tar.gz>).

271 WAVEWATCH III solves the random phase spectral action density balance equation for wavenumber-
272 direction spectra, and includes options for shallow-water applications. Propagation of a wave spectrum can
273 be solved using regular (rectilinear or curvilinear) and unstructured (triangular) grids. Source terms for
274 physical processes include parameterizations for wave growth due to the actions of wind, nonlinear resonant
275 wave-wave interactions, scattering due to wave-bottom interactions, triad interactions, dissipation due to
276 whitecapping, bottom friction, surf-breaking, and interactions with mud and ice. Source terms are integrated
277 in time using a dynamically adjusted time stepping algorithm.

278 In this application, according to the project needs, two different implementations of the model were
279 performed, with two different computational domains. The first one included the entire Mediterranean basin
280 and a further area west of the Strait of Gibraltar, to improve accuracy in the Alboran Sea (Figure 3b). The
281 second one was extended to the Atlantic Ocean (Figure 3a) to simulate the wave climate in front of the
282 ocean-facing European cities. As for boundary conditions, domains were assumed to be closed at the
283 farthest ocean boundaries. Both domains have been discretized by unstructured meshes with a variable
284 resolution up to 500 m in the coastal areas surrounding the cities of interest (Figures 3c, and 3d). The
285 resolution decreases in the rest of the domain and the minimum resolution in deep offshore areas reaches
286 about 70 km for the Mediterranean grid, and about 300 km for the Atlantic one. GEBCO, EMODnet, and
287 nautical chart bathymetries were used in different parts of the domains.

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289
 290 **Fig. 3** Finite element meshes used by the WWIII wave model (upper panels labeled with A, B, C and D) and the
 291 SHYFEM hydrodynamic model (lower panels labeled with E, F, G, H, I and L). Panels A and B show portions of the
 292 WWIII domains, which include most of the Atlantic Ocean and the entire Mediterranean Sea. High-resolution areas
 293 for Oarsoaldea (red point), Vilanova (blue point), and Massa (green point) are displayed in panels C and D. Panels E,
 294 F, and G illustrate portions of the three SHYFEM domains, covering most of the North Atlantic Ocean and the entire
 295 Mediterranean Sea, highlighting the high-resolution areas. The bottom panels (H, I and L) depict the bathymetric
 296 details of the three study sites

297

298 The output of the wave model was recorded hourly at all grid points for the integrated quantities, in
 299 particular significant wave height (H_s), mean wavelength (L_m), mean wave period (T_m), peak wave period
 300 (T_p), mean wave direction (Dir_m) and peak wave direction (Dir_p). The atmospheric dataset provided by ERA

301 Interim+EuroCordex (ALADIN63 RCM) for the evaluation data and CMIP5+EuroCordex for the other
302 data, which includes wind (uas, vas) at a frequency of 3 hours, was used as forcing.

303

304 **4.2 Water level model**

305 Future projections of storm surge events for the three study sites have been conducted using advanced
306 numerical modeling techniques. Specifically, SHYFEM (System of Hydrodynamic Finite Element
307 Modules, Umgiesser et al., 2004), an ocean model based on the finite element method, has been
308 implemented for each coastal site to simulate the temporal and spatial variability of water levels influenced
309 by atmospheric forcing, wind and atmospheric pressure.

310 SHYFEM is an open-source community model (freely downloadable at [https://github.com/SHYFEM-](https://github.com/SHYFEM-model/shyfem.git)
311 [model/shyfem.git](https://github.com/SHYFEM-model/shyfem.git)), that resolves the 3D primitive equations system, integrated over z-layers, in their
312 formulations with water levels and transports. It uses a semi-implicit algorithm for the discretization in time
313 and finite element for the spatial integration. The model has been widely used to investigate the main
314 hydrodynamics in coastal areas (e.g. Western Mediterranean Sea in Bonamano et al., 2024 and Cucco et
315 al., 2023, 2022; Umgiesser et al., 2014, 2022; Quattrocchi et al., 2021; Maicu et al., 2018; Federico et al.,
316 2017) and for real time prediction of storm surge events in several coastal sites in the Mediterranean sea,
317 e.g. the Venice Lagoon (Umgiesser et al., 2022; Bajo et al., 2007, 2019). We refer to (Umgiesser et al.,
318 2004) for a detailed overview of the model equation system, numerical treatment and parameters setup.

319 In this application, SHYFEM has been implemented in 2D mode accounting for barotropic pressure
320 gradients, wind drag and bottom friction, which are the primary forces driving the storm surge events
321 (Bloemendaal et al., 2018; Wicks et al., 2017). The model was applied to simulate the atmospheric
322 contribution to water level η , thus neglecting the non-linear interaction with tides. This approach is
323 commonly used in ocean prediction systems, in fact, the non-linear interactions between tides and surge are
324 generally small enough to allow for the linear addition of tidal and surge components thus reducing the
325 complexity of numerical experiments (Yang et al., 2023; Zijl et al., 2013; Bajo et al., 2007).

326 The water levels including tides can be derived by adding the astronomical tide to the computed η . The
327 impact on accuracy depends on tidal amplitudes, which are minimal in the Western Mediterranean Sea due
328 to very low tides (0.2-0.3 m) and slightly more significant for the Atlantic site where tidal amplitudes exceed
329 1.5 m (around 3 m, as estimated by Fernández-Montblanc et al., 2018 for the whole European coastal seas).
330 The same assumption was applied to other factors such as general circulation and climate-induced RSLR,
331 which contribute to a lesser extent to water level fluctuations in case of extreme events.

332 Three different finite element meshes have been implemented to reproduce, with varying spatial resolution,
333 the geomorphological features of the three coastal sites (Figure 3h, i, l). Each domain extends to the entire
334 basin facing each study site (the Western Mediterranean Sea for Villanova and Massa, and most of the
335 North Atlantic for Oarsoaldea) to cover the full area influenced by the main wind fetches and to eliminate
336 the need for ad hoc open boundary conditions.

337 The atmospheric dataset provided by the ALADIN63 RCM, which includes wind and atmospheric pressure
338 data (uas, vas and psl) at a 3-hour frequency, was used as forcing.

339

340 **4.3 River discharge model**

341 River floods occur when the stream or channel geometry is not sufficient to contain the incoming volume
342 of water. In order to model river floods, it is necessary to define the discharge hydrographs, i.e. the evolution
343 in time of flow rate in given cross sections. The shape of the hydrograph, the time and value of its peak,
344 and in general the streamflow generated in the channel network as a response to precipitation events, are

345 the consequences of the hydrological processes in the upstream basin. Such processes include several
346 complex mechanisms occurring at land surface (infiltration, evapotranspiration, runoff generation, hillslope
347 routing, snowmelt, groundwater recharge) that depend on many factors like basin topography, soil hydraulic
348 properties, vegetation cover and structure of the river network.

349 In this work, we have used LISFLOOD (<https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood/>), a spatially distributed
350 hydrological model developed by the Joint Research Centre (JRC) of the European Commission since 1997
351 (Van Der Knijff et al., 2008). LISFLOOD has been applied to a wide range of applications and is currently
352 used in the EFAS (European Flood Awareness System) and GLOFAS (Global Flood Awareness System)
353 (Alfieri et al., 2019). In LISFLOOD, the soil is schematised with three layers and all the main hydrological
354 processes are modeled: surface runoff, exchange of soil moisture between layers and drainage to the
355 groundwater, sub-surface and groundwater flow and flow through river channels.

356 For the calculation of potential reference evapotranspiration, potential evaporation from bare soil and open
357 water, LISFLOOD can be coupled to the LISVAP preprocessing routine (JRC, 2013), especially developed
358 for this purpose (<https://ec-jrc.github.io/lisflood-lisvap/>).

359 In this work LISFLOOD model was applied to the main rivers that cross the selected coastal cities: Frigido
360 river for Massa (catchment size ~ 70 km²), Torrent de la Piera and Torrent de San Juan for Villanova (total
361 size of the two catchments ~ 40 km²), and Oiartzun river for Oarsoaldea (catchment size ~ 85 km²). Such
362 watersheds were represented as gridded domains with 100x100 m cell size (Figure 4a, b, c).

363 For Frigido river, geomorphological and land cover characteristics were obtained from data available from
364 Tuscany Region (hydrologically conditioned DEM at 10x10 m resolution, land cover at 1:10000 scale),
365 while for the other basins data were obtained from EU-DEM v 1.1 25x25 m resolution, Copernicus Land
366 Monitoring Service (<https://land.copernicus.eu>) and ISRIC Soil Grids 250x250 m
367 (<https://www.isric.org>).

368 The meteorological forcing fields extracted from EURO-CORDEX necessary to run the LISFLOOD-
369 LISVAP models, as reported in section 3, are precipitation (1h), sea level pressure (3h), wind speed (3h),
370 minimum and maximum air temperature (daily), humidity (daily), shortwave and longwave radiation
371 (daily).

372 Output of LISFLOOD are the times series of hourly river discharge in selected points, for each
373 climatological scenario. Extreme value analysis can then be applied on these long-term time series to obtain
374 design flood peaks for the selected return periods and the resulting hydrographs to be used as BC for the
375 hydraulic simulations (whose domains are shown in figure 4d, e, f), as described in Section 5.

376

377
378 **Fig 4** Top row: View of the domains (blue shading) for the rainfall-runoff hydrological model: a) basin of Oiartzun
379 river, with outlet in Oarsoaldea, b) basin of Frigido river, with outlet in Massa b), basins of Torrent de San Juan and
380 Torrent de la Piera, with outlet in Vilanova c). Middle row: View of the domains of the 2D hydrodynamic modeling
381 (red shading): d) Oarsoaldea, e) Massa, f) Vilanova. Bottom row: Enlargement of the area close to the river mouth,
382 showing the resolution of the employed DEM to create the 2D computational domain: g) Oarsoaldea, h) Massa, i)
383 Vilanova. Base map: Google Satellite imagery (© Google 2024; Imagery © CNES / Airbus, Maxar Technologies,
384 Airbus)

385

386 **5 Modeling floods at urban-scale**

387

388 In this section, we describe the extreme value analysis to obtain the boundary conditions for the flood
389 simulations at urban scale using the hydrodynamic model implemented at each analyzed city.

390

391 **5.1 Extreme value analysis**

392 The extreme value analysis has been performed for the variables river discharge Q and total water level
393 η_{TOT} . Two return period values were determined, 25 and 100 years for each experiment (Historical, RCP4.5,
394 RCP8.5). Furthermore, for the climate projections, two different time windows were analyzed, 2011-2060
395 and 2051-2100 (Table 1).

396 In this study, the Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution was employed to model the occurrence of
397 annual maxima values of river discharge Q and total water level η_{TOT} , separately. Since our principal

398 objective is the comparison among different experiments, such a distribution allowed us to be consistent
 399 and to use the same number of events (50) for all the experiments.

400 The total water level η_{TOT} for the Massa and Vilanova cases is equal to the sum of η and the runup value,
 401 which is calculated with the Atkinson et al. (2016) equation: $R_{2\%} = 0.92 \tan\beta \sqrt{H_S L_P} + 0.16 H_S$, where
 402 $\tan\beta$ is the slope of the beach and L_P is the deep water wavelength at the peak period. Before the calculation
 403 of $R_{2\%}$, the wave height is projected along the orthogonal direction to the coastline, to account for wave
 404 direction. For Oarsoaldea the effect of runup is not included in the computations since we do not simulate
 405 waves within the port.

406 The Generalized Extreme Value (GEV) distribution can be written as follows (cumulative distribution
 407 function):

$$408 \quad F(x) = e^{-\left(1 + \xi \frac{x - \mu}{\sigma}\right)^{-\frac{1}{\xi}}}$$

409 defined for values of x for which $\xi \cdot x > \xi \cdot \mu - \sigma$. In this equation, μ is the location parameter, ξ is the shape
 410 parameter, and σ is the scale parameter. The shape parameter ξ governs the distribution type: $\xi = 0$, Type I,
 411 Gumbel distribution; $\xi > 0$, Type II, Fréchet distribution; $\xi < 0$, Type III, Weibull distribution (Coles, 2001)
 412 .

413 The parameters μ , σ , ξ are estimated from data using the maximum likelihood method. Then, the return
 414 levels x_{RP} for a given return period can be calculated as follows:

$$415 \quad x_{RP} = \mu + \frac{\sigma}{\xi} \left(\left(-\ln\left(1 - \frac{1}{RP}\right) \right)^{-\xi} - 1 \right).$$

416 To ensure robust estimates of the uncertainties associated with the return levels, the confidence intervals
 417 (CI) at the 95% significance level were calculated using parametric bootstrapping with 500 iterations
 418 (Gilleland, 2020). The statistical analysis has been performed using the R package extRemes: Extreme
 419 Value Analysis (Gilleland and Katz, 2016).

420

421 **5.2 Hydrodynamic model**

422 The effect of extreme storm surge and river flood on the analyzed coastal cities was determined using the
 423 HEC-RAS 6.4 hydrodynamic model (Brunner & US Army Corps of Engineers, 2021). The software couples
 424 the simulation of the flow within a river, solving the one-dimensional Saint-Venant equation, to the two-
 425 dimensional flow on the floodable areas, solving the shallow water equations. Once the water level within
 426 the river bed exceeds the elevation of the levees, water flows on the two-dimensional computational mesh
 427 (the opposite flow is also possible).

428 The computational domains associated with the three cities are reported in Figure 4d, e, f. Each mesh is
 429 created by overlapping the HEC-RAS computational grid to the digital elevation model (DEM) of the
 430 analyzed area. The system calculates specific elevation-volume relationships for each computational cell,
 431 representing the details of the underlying layer. This allows us to save computational time by setting a lower
 432 resolution for the HEC-RAS mesh with respect to the DEM. For the three cities of Massa, Vilanova and
 433 Oarsoaldea, the DEM is obtained from the LIDAR dataset, at a resolution of 2 m (Figure 4g, h, i). The
 434 HEC-RAS mesh elements have a reference size from 10 to 20 m, except for specific areas (e.g. close to the
 435 coastline, complex urban patterns, etc..) where they are reduced to 5 m. The river geometry is composed
 436 by the river cross sections and additional information of hydraulic structures. For the Massa and Oarsoaldea
 437 cases the geometry comes from a topographic survey, whereas for Vilanova it was extracted from the
 438 LIDAR dataset.

439 Boundary conditions (BCs) are differently set based on the simulation carried out, as reported in Table 2.
 440 For the river flood simulations the upstream BC is a time series $Q_{RP}(t)$, with peak discharge value Q_{RP} equal
 441 to the return period value. The shape of the hydrograph $Q_{RP}(t)$ is determined as follows: i) the 24 hours
 442 preceding and following the annual maxima are extracted for each year; ii) these 49 hours time series are
 443 superimposed to have maxima in phase and then averaged; iii) the averaged time series is normalized to
 444 obtain $q(t)$, having maximum equal to 1; iv) the $Q_{RP}(t)$ boundary is obtained multiplying $q(t)$ by Q_{RP} . Such
 445 a procedure is applied to every run to get the appropriate BC. The downstream BC at the sea is the mean
 446 sea level plus the RSLR, based on the reference scenario $\Delta\eta_{RSLR}$ as reported in Table 2.
 447
 448

	River (upstream) BC	Sea (downstream) BC
River flood	Time series hydrograph $Q_{RP}(t)$	Mean sea level + $\Delta\eta_{RSLR}$
Coastal flood	Constant hydrograph Q	Time series hydrograph $\eta(t)_{RP} + \Delta\eta_{Tide} + \Delta\eta_{RSLR}$

449 Table 2. Combination of upstream and downstream boundary conditions for the river and coastal flood simulations.
 450

451 For the coastal flood simulations, considering the inaccuracies inherent in long-term predictions on a
 452 century time scale (Dessay et al., 2009), a statistical approach was preferable to take into account tides and
 453 other factors contributing to the water level of the downstream BC. Specifically, for each site, delta water
 454 levels representing the maximum spring tidal amplitudes $\Delta\eta_{Tide}$ (0.2 m for Massa and for Villanova) and
 455 the predicted sea level rise on a decadal time scale $\Delta\eta_{RSLR}$ (Table 3) were linearly added to the $\eta_{RP}(t)$ time
 456 series to estimate the worst-case scenario for coastal flooding. $\eta_{RP}(t)$ is calculated following the same
 457 procedure employed for the river discharge, with peak value equal to $\eta_{TOT,RP}$. The upstream BC is a constant
 458 value for the river discharge such as the model can run without instabilities and no flood occurs.
 459

$\Delta\eta_{RSLR}$	Massa	Villanova	Oarsoaldea
RCP4.5 2011-2060	0.150 (-0.036, +0.05)	0.15 (-0.044, +0.056)	0.192 (-0.057, +0.061)
RCP4.5 2051-2100	0.351 (-0.096, 0.131)	0.349 (-0.105, +0.138)	0.412 (-0.155, +0.150)
RCP8.5 2011-2060	0.168 (-0.042, +0.057)	0.173 (-0.053, +0.062)	0.229 (-0.079, +0.073)
RCP8.5 2051-2100	0.464 (-0.137, +0.173)	0.458 (-0.136, +0.185)	0.537 (-0.208, +0.203)

460 Table 3. Values of RSLR referred to the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios, averaged over the reference period, for the analyzed cities.
 461

462 In Oarsoaldea, we used a slightly different approach for the coastal flood simulations since the tidal
 463 excursion is larger than the extreme return period values: the downstream BC is a semidiurnal tide (up to
 464 2.3 m) added to the $\Delta\eta_{RSLR}$ and to the increase due to the return period value $\Delta\eta_{RP}$.
 465 For the city of Massa a single river called Frigido is simulated and the urban area is divided into two portions
 466 adjacent to the sides of the river (Figure 4d). In Villanova, two river streams are modeled, the easternmost
 467 is the main one, called Torrent de la Piera, whereas the other one (Torrent de Sant Joan) is forced
 468 underground for about 500 meters, just before the rivermouth (Figure 4e). The two-dimensional domain is

469 split in three subdomains, one between the two rivers and two on their sides. Oiartzun is the main river
 470 modeled for Oarsoaldea, while Lintzirin is its tributary forced underground for most of its length (Figure
 471 4g). In this case the peak discharge of the minor river is scaled in proportion to the basin area (47.4 km²
 472 and 8.7 km², respectively). The two-dimensional domain is divided into two parts including the Pasaia bay
 473 area.

474

475

476 6 Results

477

478 6.1 Extremes for wave climate, water level and river discharge

479 A first comparison is performed between the annual maxima of the Historical and Evaluation runs. For the
 480 former, the years from 1973 to 2005 are considered, whereas for the latter those from 1980 to 2012, for an
 481 overall amount of 33 years each. This allows us to have an estimate of the degree of over/under-estimation
 482 we can have on the projections with respect to the actual scenario.

483

484

485 **Fig 5** Quantile-quantile plots between annual maxima from evaluation and historical runs, for the city of Massa a) and
 486 b), Villanova c) and d), and Oarsoaldea d) and e) for the total water level η_{TOT} (first column), and the peak discharge

487 Q (second column). For the city of Oarsoaldea η is reported since no runoff contribution is considered. Red dots
 488 represent the annual maxima, black dashed line is the 1:1 line

489

490 In Figure 5, the quantile-quantile plots for the three analyzed cities for both river discharge and total water
 491 level are reported. Historical and Evaluation annual maxima total water levels in Massa are in agreement
 492 (Figure 5a), whereas Historical river discharge is subject to underestimation only for the highest values
 493 (Figure 5b). Total water levels in Villanova are generally larger for the Historical run with respect to
 494 Evaluation (Figure 5c), whereas river discharge extreme values are correctly estimated except for a single
 495 data (Figure 5d). Oarsoaldea water levels are slightly overestimated by the Historical up to 0.4 m. Also
 496 river discharge values are generally overestimated up to 100 m³/s, then, the largest values tend to be
 497 underestimated (Figure 5f).

498

499

Massa	$\eta_{TOT,RP}$ [m]		Q_{RP} [m ³ /s]	
	25 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]	100 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]	25 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]	100 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]
Historical	1.736 (-0.062, +0.057)	1.804 (-0.098, +0.094)	172 (-31, +42)	227 (-63, +109)
RCP4.5 2011-2060	1.781 (-0.068, +0.041) [+2.6%]	1.838 (-0.095, +0.057) [+1.9%]	177 (-34, +53) [+2.9%]	233 (-72, +155) [+2.6%]
RCP4.5 2051- 2100	1.770 (-0.076, +0.084) [+1.95%]	1.861 (-0.124, +0.157) [+3.2%]	210 (-51, +96) [+22.1%]	307 (-115, +332) [+35.2%]
RCP8.5 2011-2060	1.719 (-0.032, +0.013) [-1.0%]	1.741 (-0.039, 0.014) [-3.5%]	201 (-36, +52) [+16.9%]	259 (-74, +136) [+14.1%]
RCP8.5 2051- 2100	1.739 (-0.050, +0.032) [+0.2%]	1.783 (-0.066, +0.047) [-1.2%]	253 (-70, +103) [+47.1%]	386 (-160 +367) [+70.0%]

500 Table 4. Return period values associated with 25 and 100 years for the different runs for the city of Massa for both the total water
 501 level $\eta_{TOT,RP}$ and the peak discharge Q_{RP} . Numbers in % (in square brackets) represent the variation relative to the historical value.
 502

503 Table 4, Table 5 and Table 6, show the results of the extreme value analysis of $\eta_{TOT,RP}$ and Q_{RP} for the city
 504 of Massa, Villanova and Oarsoaldea, respectively, together with the confidence intervals at 95%
 505 significance level (round brackets) and the percentage increase/decrease (square brackets) with respect to
 506 the Historical values.

507 For η_{TOT} in Massa, the RCP4.5 scenario shows slightly larger values with respect to the historical run,
 508 whereas the RCP8.5 has similar or slightly lower values. Conversely, extreme Q values tend to grow for
 509 both time windows and further forward in the future for both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5. Nevertheless, the
 510 estimated 100 years peak discharge shows large uncertainty values, especially for the 2051-2100 case for
 511 both RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 runs (Table 4).

512

Villanova	$\eta_{TOT,RP}$ [m]		Q_{RP} [m ³ /s]	
	25 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]	100 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]	25 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]	100 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]
Historical	1.360 (-0.055, +0.034)	1.409 (-0.079, +0.056)	91 (-20, +27)	125 (-39, +79)
RCP4.5 2011-2060	1.340 (-0.039, +0.022) [-1.5%]	1.375 (-0.053, +0.031) [-2.4%]	87 (-15, +18) [-4.4%]	107 (-27, +42) [-14.4%]
RCP4.5 2051-2100	1.375 (-0.080, +0.058) [+1.1%]	1.450 (-0.131, +0.097) [+2.9%]	107 (-22, +25) [+17.6%]	137 (-41, +59) [+9.6%]
RCP8.5 2011-2060	1.401 (-0.075, +0.053) [+3.0%]	1.473 (-0.108, +0.089) [+4.5%]	109 (-19, +26) [+19.8%]	139 (-35, +57) [+11.2%]
RCP8.5 2051-2100	1.360 (-0.059, +0.040) [+0%]	1.411 (-0.081, +0.064) [+0.1%]	116 (-23, +36) [+27.5%]	154 (-46, +83) [+23.2%]

513 Table 5. Return period values associated with 25 and 100 years for the different runs for the city of Villanova for both the total
514 water level $\eta_{TOT,RP}$ and the peak discharge Q_{RP} . Numbers in % (in square brackets) represent the variation relative to the historical
515 value.
516

517 Extreme η_{TOT} values for the city of Villanova show an increase for the RCP4.5 2051-2100 and for the
518 RCP8.5 2011-2060 scenarios (both 25 and 100 yr RPs), whereas a decrease is found for the RCP4.5 2011-
519 2060. Analogously, Q extreme values are lower than the historical for the RCP4.5 2011-2060 scenario (both
520 25 and 100 yr RPs), but an increase is observed for all the other cases (Table 5).
521

Oarsoaldea	η_{RP} [m]		Q_{RP} [m ³ /s]	
	25 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]	100 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]	25 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]	100 yr (95% CI) [variation to hist %]
Historical	0.433 (-0.025, +0.018)	0.456 (-0.035, +0.025)	169 (-30, +34)	209 (-54, +87)
RCP4.5 2011- 2060	0.444 (-0.039, 0.031) [+2.5%]	0.486 (-0.061, +0.060) [+6.6%]	168 (-27, +27) [-0.6%]	201 (-46, +56) [-3.8%]
RCP4.5 2051-2100	0.395 (-0.021, 0.016) [-8.8%]	0.416 (-0.030, +0.026) [-8.8%]	176 (-19, +12) [+4.1%]	195 (-27, +22) [-6.7%]
RCP8.5 2011- 2060	0.423 (-0.039, +0.035) [-2.3%]	0.462 (-0.059, +0.077) [+1.7%]	163 (-18, +15) [-3.5%]	182 (-27, +32) [-12.9%]
RCP8.5 2051- 2100	0.416 (-0.022, +0.013) [-3.9%]	0.436 (-0.030, +0.018) [-4.4%]	173 (-20, +18) [+2.4%]	194 (-31, +35) [-7.2%]

522 Table 6. Return period values associated with 25 and 100 years for the different runs for the city of Oarsoaldea for both the water
523 level η_{RP} and the peak discharge Q_{RP} . Numbers in % (in square brackets) represent the variation relative to the historical value.
524

525 Concerning extreme water levels in Oarsoaldea, an increase for the RCP4.5 2011-2060 (both 25 and 100
526 yr RPs) is observed, while all the other cases show decrease or substantial invariance. The extreme river
527 discharge is not subject to significant variations for the 25 years RP, whereas a general slight decrease is
528 observed for the 100 years RP for all scenarios.

529

530 6.2 Flooded areas

531 The envelope of the water depth simulated through the hydrodynamic model for coastal and riverine floods
532 with a 100 yr RP are reported in Figure 6 and Figure 7, respectively.

533 More specifically, results are reported for the RCP4.5 2051-2100 and RCP8.5 2011-2060 for the three
534 analyzed cities. The remaining figures of flooded areas, that is: the 100 yr RP coastal floods (Figure S1)
535 and 100 yr RP riverine floods (Figure S2) cases, and all the 25 y RP cases (Figure S3 for coastal flood and
536 Figure S4 for riverine flood), are reported in the Supplementary material.

537 For the city of Massa, the simulations of the future scenarios show an increase in flooded areas, especially
538 for the RCP4.5 2051-2100 (Figure 6a, d, g). Such a case shows a rise of 60% in flooded volume with respect
539 to the Historical case, whereas the increase is 7% for the RCP8.5 2011-2060 100 yr RP (Table 7). In general,
540 coastal flood volume increase in Massa is larger for the furthest time window in the future.

541 Storm surges in Villanova mainly impact the beach area and the surroundings of the port (Figure 6b, e, h),
542 and the rise in flooded volume compared to the Historical case is at most 20% (RCP4.5 2051-2100 25 yr
543 RP, Table 7).
544

545

546 **Fig 6** Hazard maps associated to the 100 years return period coastal flood event for the city of Massa: Historical a),
547 RCP4.5 2051-2100 d), RCP8.5 2011-2060 g); for the city of Villanova: Historical b), RCP4.5 2051-2100 e), RCP8.5

548 2011-2060 h); for the city of Oarsoaldea: Historical c), RCP4.5 2051-2100 f), RCP8.5 2011-2060 i). Base map: Google
549 Satellite imagery (© Google 2024; Imagery © CNES / Airbus, Maxar Technologies, Airbus)

550

551 For Oarsoaldea, the hydrodynamic simulations of coastal flooding do not show substantial variations
552 between the Historical case and the projections (Figure 6c, f, i). This is confirmed by the flooded volume
553 variation which is at most 3% for the RCP8.5 2051-2100 100 yr RP (Table 7).

554

555

556 **Fig 7** Hazard maps associated to the 100 years return period riverine flood event for the city of Massa: Historical a),
557 RCP4.5 2051-2100 d), RCP8.5 2011-2060 g); for the city of Vilanova: Historical b), RCP4.5 2051-2100 e), RCP8.5
558 2011-2060 h); for the city of Oarsoaldea: Historical c), RCP4.5 2051-2100 f), RCP8.5 2011-2060 i). Base map: Google
559 Satellite imagery (© Google 2024; Imagery © CNES / Airbus, Maxar Technologies, Airbus)

560

561 The results of the 100 yr RP riverine floods hydrodynamic simulations are reported in Figure 7. For the city
562 of Massa a substantial increase in the flooded area for the RCP4.5 2051-2100 (Figure 7d) and RCP8.5 2011-
563 2060 (Figure 7g) with respect to Historical case (Figure 7a), is observed. This is consistent with the rise in
564 flooded volume reported in Table 7, where an increase larger than 200% is seen for both the RPs associated
565 with the RCP8.5 2051-2100 case.

566 The visual comparison of Figure 7b, e, h does not allow to clearly detect an increase/decrease in flooded
567 area with respect to the Historical case for the city of Vilanova. However, the computation of flooded

568 volume variation shows an increase up to 33% for all cases except for RCP4.5 2011-2060 for both RPs
 569 (Table 7).
 570 Oarsoaldea exhibits a different behavior since the Historical events cause larger floods with respect to most
 571 part of the projections. Even for this city the visual comparison of water depths does not allow us to identify
 572 increase/decrease in flooded areas (Figure 7c, f, i), but the results reported in Table 6 show that rise in
 573 flooded volume around 11% is observed only for the 25 yr RPs for the RCP4.5 for the 2051-2100 time
 574 window. All other cases show a decrease in flooded volume, up to -38% for RCP8.5 2011-2060 100 yr RP.
 575

Analyzed city	Run	Coastal flood		Riverine flood	
		25 years	100 years	25 years	100 years
Massa	RCP4.5 2011-2060	+20%	+18%	+7%	+9%
	RCP4.5 2051-2100	+49%	+60%	+84%	+124%
	RCP8.5 2011-2060	+14%	+7%	+51%	+44%
	RCP8.5 2051-2100	+68%	+68%	+218%	+261%
Vilanova	RCP4.5 2011-2060	+1%	+0%	-8%	-20%
	RCP4.5 2051-2100	+8%	+10%	+17%	+11%
	RCP8.5 2011-2060	+6%	+8%	+23%	+15%
	RCP8.5 2051-2100	+9%	+9%	+30%	+33%
Oarsoaldea	RCP4.5 2011-2060	+1%	+1%	-3%	-11%
	RCP4.5 2051-2100	+1%	+1%	+11%	-17%
	RCP8.5 2011-2060	+1%	+1%	-14%	-33%
	RCP8.5 2051-2100	+2%	+3%	+1%	-38%

576 Table 7. Percentage change of the flooded volume with respect to the historical run for the three cities of Massa, Vilanova and
 577 Oarsoaldea, for the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 (2011-2060, 2051-2100) scenarios for both the 25 and 100 years return periods.
 578

579

580

581 **7 Discussion**

582

582 Assessing the impacts of future climate scenarios on extreme flood events in coastal cities requires a huge
583 effort due to the need to integrate processes across multiple scales, from synoptic scale (i.e. storms spanning
584 ~100-1000 km) to local scale. At the urban scale, specific geomorphic features such as landscape elevation
585 and structural elements can significantly influence flood extent. To address this complexity, we
586 implemented a multiscale modeling chain tailored for three of the CCLLs under the SCORE Project, but
587 that can be easily generalized to other coastal cities. We employed unstructured grids modelling approaches
588 to simulate wave climate (WWIII) and water levels (SHYFEM). These were integrated with the distributed
589 hydrological model LISFLOOD, and finally coupled within high-resolution urban hydrodynamic
590 simulations, to capture the interaction between extreme events and urban-specific characteristics, achieving
591 the spatial granularity needed to capture critical urban-scale flood dynamics. However, this level of detail
592 comes with a huge computational effort: each of the three models ran simulations equivalent to nearly 300
593 years, repeated for all analyzed cities.

594 This consideration was the most significant factor influencing our choice of using a single RCM (and GCM)
595 rather than a multi-model ensemble approach. In addition, data availability from EURO-CORDEX for all
596 required variables at a sufficient output frequency and covering the Evaluation, Historical, RCP4.5 and
597 RCP8.5 runs was ensured only by the ALADIN63 model driven by the ERA-Interim reanalysis and the
598 CNRM-CM5 GCM. We have given priority to have a continuous dataset at the cost of giving up an
599 uncertainty estimate based on multi-model ensemble. However, such an estimate, associated with the
600 extreme values from the analyzed time series, was recovered in the statistical analysis by calculating
601 confidence intervals through the bootstrap method.

602 The comparison between the annual maxima from the Evaluation and Historical runs (Figure 5), together
603 with the information reported in Tables 4, 5 and 6, enables us to assess the reliability of the coastal and
604 riverine hazard maps (Figures 6 and Figure 7).

605 Future coastal floods in Massa do not show significant variations in terms of event magnitude compared to
606 the Historical period. Indeed, the increase/decrease ranges from -3.5% to +3.2 with a predominance of
607 positive values (Table 3). Considering the 95% CIs, the variability generally lies between +2.5% and +5%
608 of the calculated extreme value for the 2011-2060 and 2051-2100 time windows, respectively. Although an
609 increase in wave height is projected for the Ligurian-Tyrrhenian Sea (De Leo et al., 2024), several factors
610 may contribute to the observed invariance in total water levels for Massa. The shallow bathymetry in front
611 of Massa (Figure 3) can act as a sort of filter for the highest offshore waves, leading to a sort of upper limit
612 for the wave height close to the shoreline which, in turn, affects the total water level through the runup
613 equation. Additionally, the very high resolution of the modeling near the coast captures local-scale effects
614 that are often missed by lower-resolution models. Furthermore, the sensitivity of runup to wave height for
615 Massa's beach slope, combined with the wavelengths associated with the highest waves (70-95 m) is
616 modest, approximately 0.2-0.25 m. This means that a 1 m increase in wave height produces 0.2-0.25 m
617 increase in runup. As a consequence, any increase/decrease in wave climate is partially damped. Actually,
618 the main driver in producing significant differences in flooded volume is the RSLR (Table 3), which causes
619 the storm surge to penetrate farther inland, resulting in larger flooded volumes (Table 7).

620 Riverine floods for the RCPs projections in Massa show a substantial increase, even more evident for the
621 2051-2100 time window. However, this is accompanied by an equal increase in uncertainty. Indeed, the
622 width of the 95% CI is almost 1.5 times the 100 yr RP for both the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 2051-2100. Despite
623 this, the overall increase in extreme Q_{RP} for all the analyzed scenarios and time windows confirms an
624 increment in future peak river discharges. However, such extremes could be slightly underestimated as
625 observable from the QQ-plot of Evaluation and Historical annual maxima (Figure 5b). Notwithstanding,

626 their impact on the ground is further augmented by the increase in relative sea level, whereby the higher
627 downstream boundary condition hinders the flow toward the sea, resulting in a substantial increase in the
628 flooded volume (Table 7).

629 The extension of the flooded area for Vilanova appears not to be affected by storm surges principally due
630 to the characteristics of the beach zone which is separated from the urban area by a steep positive gradient
631 in the land elevation which makes the latter higher. A substantial equivalence between the Historical and
632 the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 extreme values is observed and the $\Delta\eta_{\text{RSLR}}$ ranges between 0.15 and 0.458 m
633 (Table 3). Even though the increase in flooded volume is always positive (Table 7), the flooded area is not
634 enlarged (Figure 6b, e, h) and the only area which is interested in an enlargement of the flooded surface is
635 the one adjacent to the port.

636 The riverine floods associated with projections are generally characterized by an increase in flooded volume
637 with respect to the Historical (from +11% to +33%), but for the RCP4.5 2011-2060 25 and 100 yr RPs (-
638 8% and -20%), as reported in Table 7. Concerning the Q_{RP} values, the higher the extreme value, the larger
639 the CI width. However, a substantial increase in river discharge is observable, in agreement with the flooded
640 volume. The comparison of annual maxima from Evaluation and Historical (Figure 5d) suggests no
641 underestimation/overestimation, even if the largest value could lead one to think of an overestimation. The
642 additional increase in flooded volume (Table 7) compared to the maxima in river discharge (Table 5) is
643 primarily attributed to the RSLR, similar to the findings for Massa.

644 For the city of Oarsoaldea the port area has been designed to face tidal excursions around 2 m. The extreme
645 values associated with both 25 and 100 yr RP range between 0.395 and 0.486 m. Table 5 reports increases
646 (RCP4.5 2011-2060) and decreases (RCP4.5 2051-2100 and RCP8.5 2051-2100) of the extreme water level
647 for the projections compared to the Historical, consistent with the findings of Vousdoukas et al. (2017).
648 The modest rise in flooded volume (+1% to +3%, Table 7) is mainly attributable to the RSLR.

649 For river discharge, a generalized decrease in peak Q_{RP} values is observed, with the width of the 95% CI of
650 the same order of magnitude of the variation with respect to the Historical period, and an expected slight
651 underestimation of the projected extremes (Figure 5f).

652 The use of annual maxima to perform the EVA has the disadvantage of eliminating a lot of significant data.
653 To make greater use of the time series produced, we performed two additional analyses for the city of Massa
654 for both $\eta_{\text{TOT}}(t)$ and $Q(t)$. We calculated the cumulative time a variable persists over a fixed threshold, that
655 is chosen as the 99.5%-ile and the 99.9%-ile of the Historical period time series for the total water level and
656 river discharge, respectively (Figure 8a and 9a). Furthermore, we determined the number of events per year
657 higher than specific values, clustering the events by decade (Figure 8b and 9b).

658 Figure 8a shows that the increase in RSL is the main driver for the η_{TOT} increase for the cumulative time
659 above a certain high level. It is also confirmed by Figure 8b where a trend in the increase of extreme events,
660 without the effect of RSLR, is not clearly observable.

661

662
 663 **Fig 8** a) Cumulative duration of total water level above the 99.5 %-ile in days per year for HIST (green line), RCP4.5
 664 (red line), RCP8.5 (black line), RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 plus the effect of RSLR (red dashed line and black dashed line,
 665 respectively), for the city of Massa. Number of events per year with peak values larger than specific values, grouped
 666 by decades for: HIST b), RCP4.5 c) and RCP8.5 d)
 667

668 Concerning river discharge, a slight positive trend for the cumulative time $Q(t)$ persists above the 99.9%-
 669 ile Historical value, is detectable (Figure 9a). Moreover, an increase in the number of extreme events is
 670 observed, especially for the RCP8.5 scenario, even if the obtained patch is quite noisy. This can be ascribed
 671 to the fact that we used only one RCM.
 672

673
 674 **Fig 9** a) Cumulative duration of water discharge above the 99.9 %-ile in days per year for HIST (green line), RCP4.5
 675 (red line), RCP8.5 (black line), RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 plus the effect of RSLR (red dashed line and black dashed line,
 676 respectively), for the city of Massa. Number of events per year with peak values larger than specific values, grouped
 677 by decades for: HIST b), RCP4.5 c) and RCP8.5 d)
 678

679 A potential limitation concerning the analysis of extreme events is related to compound events (Ghanbari
 680 et al., 2020; Gori & Lin, 2022). In this work we consider non-interacting storm surges and river discharges.
 681 Such a choice is aimed at simplifying the approach and having greater control on each driver of a flood
 682 event. Furthermore, the extreme value analysis of compound events lead to some difficulties and
 683 approximations related to the identification of a “compound event”. In general, focusing only on two
 684 variables, we look for large values, in one or both variables, which are temporally distant less than a specific
 685 threshold. The method to identify “compound events” varies on the basis of the different studies and scales.
 686 This aspect, together with the choice of the couple of values associated with a specific RP curve, tends to
 687 enhance the complexity and the degrees of freedom of the problem. Considering the present work as an
 688 introductory paper describing the whole modeling chain and its applications, and given the availability of
 689 continuous time series, we intend to pursue future research by focusing directly on impacts. That is, we
 690 intend to run the hydrodynamic model using as BCs the whole time series (excluding the periods where
 691 both Q and η_{TOT} are low), and analyze the statistical properties of the water depth as a consequence of flood
 692 events. In such a way it is possible to by-pass all the issues related to the definition and identification of
 693 compound events. Nevertheless, the availability of these long term simulated discharge time series can also
 694 be a valuable dataset for further analysis on hydrological regimes e.g. droughts.

695 It is important to stress that the errors which accumulate along the modeling chains are difficult to estimate
 696 and are the results of unavoidable approximations. Furthermore, we are running hydrodynamic simulations

697 where the environment (e.g. buildings, structure, etc...) do not change in time, which is an unlikely
698 circumstance. As a consequence, obtained results have to be considered as an indication of a trend rather
699 than a solid prediction of the future.

700 On the one hand, we are making a strong assumption, considering the surrounding environment does not
701 change over time. On the other hand, the knowledge of specific characteristics of the analyzed area are
702 crucial in modeling the impact of flood events. A coarse starting DEM of around 20 m resolution cannot
703 even resolve streets and spaces between buildings, potentially blocking the flow and significantly changing
704 the flooding pattern. These are aspects that have to be taken into account when evaluating the obtained
705 results associated with uncertain future scenarios.

706

707 **8 Conclusion and outlook**

708 In this work we present a modeling chain to transfer synoptic scale atmospheric information to the scale of
709 coastal cities with the goal of estimating changes in the impact of extreme riverine and coastal flood events
710 - specifically in terms of flooded area and volume - under the RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 climate change scenarios,
711 compared to Historical conditions. We use atmospheric data from the ALADIN63 RCM from the EURO-
712 CORDEX dataset to drive three numerical models: WWIII for wave climate, SHYFEM for water levels,
713 and LISFLOOD for river discharge. Model outputs are then processed to generate synthetic extreme events,
714 which are then used to simulate coastal and riverine floods through a high-resolution hydrodynamic model
715 (HEC-RAS). This model is specifically implemented for the domains of three coastal cities selected within
716 the SCORE Project: Massa (Italy), Vilanova i la Geltrù, and Oarsoaldea (Spain). Wave climate data are
717 further used to calculate wave runup, which is combined with water levels to determine total water levels
718 η_{TOT} .

719 The extreme value analysis of total water levels η_{TOT} and river discharge Q reveals both increase and
720 decrease in RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 extremes compared to Historical extremes, depending on the different
721 locations, with larger uncertainties associated with high extreme values and longer-term projections (2051-
722 2100). The increase/decrease in flooded volume is not necessarily related to increase/decrease in extremes
723 but it depends by relative sea-level rise RSLR and to specific local features of each coastal city.

724 Massa is particularly vulnerable to RSLR, which facilitates the inland propagation of coastal floods,
725 increasing the water volume up to 68%. Additionally, RSLR hinders river flow into the sea, exacerbating
726 riverine floods and potentially doubling water volume. This is further compounded by an increase in future
727 extreme river discharge (ranging from +2.9% to +70%), especially under the RCP8.5 scenario. In contrast,
728 Vilanova i la Geltrù is not significantly affected by storm surges due to its geomorphic structure, whereas
729 the riverine extreme floods tend to generally increase in the future according to RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 (up to
730 +27.5% for peak river discharge and +33% for water volume). Oarsoaldea, on the other hand, is well
731 protected against storm surges and the flood extension appears to be relatively insensitive to the differences
732 between Historical, RCP4.5 and RCP8.5 scenarios. Riverine floods in Oarsoaldea show a decrease in extent
733 for the 100 yr RP but slightly increase for the 25 yr RP in the 2051-2100 timeplay. These results reflect the
734 complex interplay between extreme events and RSLR.

735 This study highlights the importance of employing high resolution modeling, as local characteristics
736 significantly influence flood impacts and the analysis of the effects of future extreme events.

737 Future developments include the use of long-term time series of η_{TOT} and Q to continuously force the
738 hydrodynamic model, excluding periods associated with low values. This impact-based approach could
739 eliminate the need for EVA for different events, including compound events and enables a direct analysis

740 of their interaction on the ground, providing a statistical assessment of water depth, flood extent and water
741 volume time series.

742

743 **Author contributions**

744 **B.M.:** conceptualization, formal analysis, investigation, methodology, software, visualization, writing -
745 original draft, writing - review and editing. **C.F.:** conceptualization, investigation, methodology, writing -
746 original draft. **C.A.:** conceptualization, investigation, methodology, visualization, writing - original draft.

747 **T.S.:** conceptualization, investigation, methodology, writing - original draft. **A.I.:** formal analysis, project
748 administration, investigation. **P.R.:** writing - original draft, writing - review & editing. **M.R.:** investigation,
749 visualization, writing - review & editing. **P.M.:** data curation, investigation, visualization. **S.M.:** formal
750 analysis, investigation, writing - review & editing. **V.G.:** data curation. **O.A.:** conceptualization, funding
751 acquisition, project administration, writing - review and editing. **C.M.:** project administration. **G.S.:**
752 funding acquisition, project administration, writing - review and editing. **B.C.:** conceptualization,
753 supervision, funding acquisition, project administration, writing - review and editing.

754

755

756 **Competing interests**

757 The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

758

759

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